

THE EFFECT OF FIBER MICROSTRUCTURE AND FIBER-MATRIX INTERFACIAL ADHESION ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COIR FIBRE COMPOSITES

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1. Introduction

The interest in using natural fibers in composite materials has strongly increased over the past decades thanks to their good mechanical properties in combination with environment-friendly characteristics. In this research, Vietnamese coir fibers are studied and modified for use in composite materials. To be efficiently used in composite materials, the microstructure and the mechanical properties of coir fibers are first characterized. Secondly, the surface of natural fibers has a complex morphology with chemical heterogeneity and relatively high roughness, which strongly influences the fiber-matrix interfacial adhesion. Therefore, it is important to acquire a systematic understanding of the fiber-matrix interfacial interactions in these composites. Lastly, unidirectional (UD) composites of coir fiber in both thermoplastic and thermoset matrices are examined to evaluate the possible value of coir fiber for composites. The correlation between the fiber microstructure, fiber properties, fiber-matrix interface and the final properties of the composites will be discussed.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

Fibers

Vietnamese coir fibers used in the study were extracted from the husk shell of coconuts with a purely mechanical extraction process. The fibers were then soaked in hot water at 70°C for 2h, washed with ethanol, rinsed with de-ionized water and dried in a vacuum oven at 90°C. These fibers are named untreated coir fiber (Ucoir) in this work. The

treated coir fibers (Tcoir) were obtained using 5% NaOH solution for 2h at room temperature, then washed thoroughly with de-ionized water and dried in a vacuum oven as described above. The alkali treatment was expected to remove wax and fatty substances on the untreated fibers.

Matrices

Both thermoplastic and thermoset polymers were used as matrices for untreated and treated fibres. The thermoplastics comprised of polypropylene (PP), polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) and 0.3% maleic anhydride grafted polypropylene (MAPP). The PP was an unmodified grade supplied by Propex. The PVDF was provided by Solvay and the MAPP was supplied by Dupont. As thermoset system, the epoxy Epikote 828 and hardener Diaminocyclohexane were used.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Characterization of fiber microstructure

The microstructure of technical coir fibers was examined using SEM and X-ray tomography (SEM-CT). The fiber cross-sections were taken using a Philips XL 30 FEG scanning electron microscope. The images provide the organization of the elementary fibers inside the technical fiber and the microfibril angles. SEM-CT was used to scan segments of the fibre. With the help of the computer software SkyScan, a 3D structure of the sample in a non-destructive way was built up, which includes internal object details of the fiber [1]. In this way, also the fiber porosity is characterized.

2.2.2 Single fiber tensile testing

Tensile testing of single fibers was performed on an Instron 5943 integrated with a camera system for optical strain measurement. Speckles were created on the fiber surface so that the camera system could map the fiber strain during tensile loading. The recorded strain mapping data were analyzed using Limess software, and the calculated strains were then linked with the tensile load data to plot the stress-strain behavior of the fibers.

2.2.3 Wetting measurement and fiber surface characterization

Wetting measurements of the fibers and the matrices are carried out to obtain their static equilibrium contact angles in various liquids [1], and these are used to estimate the surface energies comprising of different components [2, 3]. The work of adhesion is calculated for each composite system, accordingly.

Besides, fibre surface chemistry is studied by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) to have more information about functional groups at the fiber surface.

2.2.4 Fiber pull-out test

The adhesion at the composite interface was evaluated using single fiber pull-out tests. To prepare the pull-out test samples, coir fibers were placed in a mould in which matrix films are stacked on two sides of the fibers. Using the compression molding technique with a hot press, the pull-out samples were made at 175 °C for PP and 185 °C for PVDF and MAPP respectively, and at 10 bar pressure for all samples. In the obtained samples, the embedded fiber length into the matrix was controlled by punching a hole through the fiber and matrix at the correct location.

2.2.5 Mechanical test of UD composites

Mechanical properties of UD coir fiber composites with both thermoplastic and thermoset matrices were assessed by flexural 3 point bending tests according to ASTM D790M, and unnotched Izod impact tests following ISO 179.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Microstructure and mechanical properties of coir fibers

Fig. 1 presents a SEM image of the coir fiber cross section and a 3D fiber model built up from SEM-CT scanning images. This shows that technical coir fibers comprise of plenty of elementary fibers and a lacuna at the centre. The elementary fiber is built up by two main cell walls which consist of bundles of microfibrils aligned in a high angle to the fiber axis.

Fig. 1. Internal structure of coir fiber (a) determination of fiber porosity using SEM-CT (b) SEM image of elementary fibers shows cell walls and microfibrils.

The analysis of the 3D scan of coir fiber also provides fiber porosity, from which coir fiber appears to have high porosity at 22 to 30% .

Fig. 2. Tensile test of single coir fiber with optical strain mapping

The tensile test of single coir fiber with an optical strain mapping system is shown in Fig. 2. The movement of speckles on the fiber surface was followed by a camera; then data analysis was done with the software Limes. Subsequently, E-modulus and strain-to-failure of the fiber were calculated and are shown in Table 1. The properties of the fibers are comparable with previously reported results [4, 5], which show high elongation at failure, but the fibers are not so strong and stiff. This can be explained by the high micro-fibrillar angle (MFA); the microfibrils are reoriented to the fiber direction during tensile loading.

Table 1. Tensile properties of coir fibres

Fibre	E-Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	Strain-to-failure (%)
Untreated coir	3.8 ± 1.0	167.7 ± 39.3	$18.0 - 36.7$

3.2. Fiber-matrix interfacial adhesion

In this study, an integrated physical-chemical-micromechanical approach, including wetting measurements, fiber surface characterization and micromechanical interface testing, is implemented to investigate the fiber-matrix interfacial compatibility and adhesion of the coir fiber composites.

Surface energies and work of adhesion

Table 2. Surface energies of fibers and matrices estimated following the Owens-Wendt approach

Fibre/Matrix	Surface energy (mJ/m ²) disperse-polar (Owens-Wendt)		
	γ_s	γ_s^d	γ_s^p
Ucoir	40.4 ± 3.9	35.1 ± 3.6	5.3 ± 1.5
Tcoir	42.2 ± 4.2	33.5 ± 3.7	8.7 ± 2.0
PP	30.7 ± 4.0	27.1 ± 3.7	3.6 ± 1.4
PVDF	37.2 ± 1.1	30.8 ± 1.0	6.4 ± 0.5
MAPP	28.6 ± 6.4	23.6 ± 5.8	5.0 ± 2.8

Surface energies of the fibers and matrices were determined and are shown in Table 2. It can be seen that the untreated fibers seem to be relatively

hydrophobic with a low polar fraction of the surface energy. 5% Alkali treated fibers have higher surface energy with an increased polar fraction. For the matrices, the surface energies of PP and MAPP are quite similar and stay at low values. As expected, the surface energy of PVDF is higher than that of PP with a relatively high polar fraction.

Fig. 3. Typical C 1s spectra comprising of the decomposition into four components C1-C4 for (a) untreated coir (b) alkali treated coir.

Fig. 3 presents the surface chemical composition of the untreated and treated fibers, providing relative atomic percentages of the elements, the oxygen-carbon ratio and decomposition of the C 1s peak into four sub-peaks C1-C4. These represent: carbon solely linked to carbon or hydrogen C-C or C-H (C1), carbon singly bound to oxygen or nitrogen C-O or C-N (C2), carbon doubly bound to oxygen O-C-O or C=O (C3) and carbon involved in ester or carboxylic acid functions O=C-O (C4). For untreated coir fiber, a high proportion of C1 and low proportion of C2-C4 suggests a combination of hydrocarbon rich waxes and lignin existing on the fiber surface as was discussed in detail in a previous study [1]. After treatment with alkali, C1 decreases while C2-C4 increase, which shows that more lignin as binder of elementary fibers (and possibly also cellulose) is exposed on the surface of the treated fibers after mainly the waxes are removed [6]. A correlation is found with the result of the wetting measurements, where higher surface energy and polarity are determined after removing waxes by alkali treatment.

In Table 3, the calculated work of adhesion shows a higher value for coir fiber in PVDF in comparison with that in PP and MAPP, which is mainly thanks to the higher surface energy and polar component of

PVDF. It also can be seen that alkali treatment somewhat improves the work of adhesion of all fiber-matrix systems, which can be partially attributed to the higher surface energy and polar component of the fibers. In coir fiber – PVDF, the surface energy components of both untreated and treated fibers are quite well matched leading to high work of adhesion and a low value of interfacial energy. For PP and MAPP systems, the improvement in work of adhesion for treated fibers is not expected to be significant, since the compatibility is relatively low, caused by mismatching surface energies and relatively high interfacial energy.

Table 3. Work of adhesion, apparent IFSS in the single fiber pull-out test; and transverse strength in 3PB of UD composites

Composite	W_a (mJ/m^2)	Trans. strength (MPa)	IFSS (MPa) at 0.5mm embedded length
Ucoir /PP	70.4 ± 4.0	3.1 ± 0.6	3.2 ± 0.3
Tcoir /PP	71.5 ± 4.1	4.4 ± 0.7	4.1 ± 0.4
Ucoir /PVDF	77.4 ± 2.8	16.6 ± 2.7	6.7 ± 0.9
Tcoir /PVDF	79.2 ± 2.9	21.5 ± 2.8	8.2 ± 0.2
Ucoir /MAPP	67.9 ± 5.9	21.0 ± 1.3	8.8 ± 0.4
Tcoir /MAPP	69.4 ± 6.1	19.1 ± 1.2	8.3 ± 1.0

Practical adhesion

The interfacial strength of the composites measured by 3 point bending in transverse direction and the IFSS from the pull-out test are shown in Table 3. As can be seen, the higher transverse strength and IFSS indicate a better interfacial adhesion in the case of coir fibers with PVDF and MAPP as compared to PP. There is an improvement in interfacial strength for treated fibers with PP and PVDF in comparison with that of untreated coir, while the interfacial strength is similar for both untreated and treated fiber with MAPP.

When the work of adhesion is considered to correspond to the practical adhesion, the results suggest that the higher interfacial adhesion of coir fibers with PVDF compared with PP can be attributed to higher fiber-matrix physico-chemical interaction corresponding with the work of adhesion. Whilst the improvement of interfacial adhesion for

coir fibers with MAPP compared with PP can probably be attributed to a chemical adhesion mechanism, where maleic anhydride functionality of the MAPP reacts covalently with OH functionality on the fibres.

An efficiency factor is used to compare the influence of interfacial adhesion on the composite strength. It is the ratio of experimental longitudinal strength over the calculated value following the rule of mixtures. It can be seen in Fig. 4 that there is a good agreement between the interfacial adhesion and the composite strength.

Fig. 4. Transverse bending strength and efficiency factor of longitudinal tensile strength of different coir fiber composites.

3.3 Mechanical properties of UD coir fiber composites

The flexural properties of coir fiber UD composites are assessed by 3 point bending in longitudinal direction. Because the fiber volume fractions of the composites are different, an efficiency factor and normalized values (to the same 50% fiber volume fraction) of E-modulus and strength will be used to have a good comparison between different systems, as shown in Fig. 5. The results indicate that coir/PVDF and coir/epoxy are stiffer compared to coir/PP and coir/MAPP systems, which is correlated to the stiffness of the matrices. For the composite strength, coir/PVDF composites give the strongest systems. The effect of fiber treatment can also be observed with the improvement of strength in treated

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fiber systems with PVDF and to a lesser extent with epoxy matrix.

Higher flexural strength and stiffness are found in treated fiber composites, probably thanks to better interfacial wetting and adhesion which can be seen by higher efficiency factors.

Fig. 5. Flexural properties of UD coir composites normalized to fiber volume fraction of 50%.

The impact strengths of coir/PP and coir/epoxy composites with the same fibre volume fraction of 40% are presented in Fig. 6, and compared to values for the neat polymers. The impact strength of coir polypropylene composite is not significantly different from that of neat polypropylene, while coir fibres can improve the toughness of the epoxy by minimum a factor of three, when the impact strength is considered as toughness indicator. In tough PP matrix, it seems the high strain to failure of coir fibre does not play an important role to decide the final impact resistance of the composite. On the other hand, the fibre provides a high contribution to the improvement of toughness of the brittle epoxy matrix.

Fig. 6. Impact strength of UD coir fiber composites.

4. Conclusions

The high microfibrillar angle in coir fibers leads to a low stiffness in fiber direction and to high elongation to failure thanks to reorientation of the microfibrils under tensile loading.

There has been a good agreement between the results of the wetting analysis and those of the composite interface mechanical tests. The combination of different characterization techniques has offered a deeper understanding of the interfacial adhesion and compatibility in coir fiber composites.

The mechanical properties of coir fiber composites reflect well the results from the fiber properties and composite interface characterizations. The results also show that coir fibers have potential for application in impact loaded composites.

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